
Implementation of Differentiation Learning with Scaffolding Strategy to Success Summative Assessments at MTsN 01 Bengkalis

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ABSTRACT: This research aims to implement differentiated learning with the Scaffolding strategy in success summative assessments students' Arabic language learning outcomes. This research is motivated by the existence of an independent learning curriculum and requires teachers to apply strategies or methods that are in accordance with the independent learning curriculum. This type of research is Classroom Action Research. Data collection using test instruments. The results of this research are based on the results of the research that has been carried out, it can be concluded that the application of differentiated learning with the Scaffolding strategy in learning Arabic at MTsN 1 Bengkalis can success summative assessments students. The success students in summative assessments can be seen from the average percentage of completeness of student summative assessments outcomes in cycle I of 66%, which has increased to 94% in cycle II.

KEYWORDS: Independent Learning Curriculum, Scaffolding Method, Success Summative Test

INTRODUCTION

Among the aims of education as stated in law number 20 of 2003 is "...to develop the potential of students so that they become human beings who have faith and are devoted to God Almighty, have noble character, are healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent and become democratic and responsible citizens".

Currently, education continues to develop as time changes and develops; its development is dynamic along with the emergence of various research facts and studies on education itself. This does not mean that this statement is directed at prioritizing the quality of education now compared to education in the past, because in any case this is not feasible considering differences in educational conditions, situations and demands from the past and the present.

In an effort to create such ideal Indonesian people as stated in the law quote above, it is necessary to have a quality education process that is accommodating to the various factual conditions of Indonesian society. Starting from a thorough curriculum planning process, maximizing curriculum implementation which is fully supported by various educational components, to evaluating and improving the various obstacles encountered in a comprehensive and continuous manner.

In a curriculum changes are made because the curriculum is a form of necessity, the greater the changes in human life, the greater the curriculum will be changed. If the cycle is not changed, stagnation will occur in human life. Why?, because the curriculum is an instrument that will change life and sustain life from all the changes that exist today, it cannot be applied as "Instead of the minister, change the curriculum" as is often discussed, but it should be "Instead of times, change the curriculum".

At the end of 2019, Covid-19 emerged for approximately three years until 2022, this is an important reason for changes to the curriculum. Therefore, there is a loss of learning for all students, especially throughout Indonesia, so a climate change policy is needed, there is a special cycle designed during the pandemic, namely the "Emergency Curriculum". This cycle also has special treatment, if the cycle is normal then it is not good to continue. , because this curriculum has become normal, the true nature of the curriculum has returned.

One of the newest curricula implemented in Indonesia is the Independent Learning Curriculum. The independent learning curriculum has characteristics, namely: 1) Project-based learning which aims to develop soft skills and character according to the Pancasila student profile. 2) Focus on essential material, so there is time for in-depth learning for basic competencies such as literacy and numeracy. 3) Teacher flexibility to carry out differentiated learning based on the learning styles and abilities of the students. (Wijaya et al., 2022, p. 1504)

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One of the facts often encountered by educators in classroom learning is the heterogeneous condition of students both in terms of gender, age and background which results in the emergence of differences in students in terms of interests, learning styles and their ability to receive information from students. Lessons delivered. This will become an obstacle for both educators and students if it is not anticipated wisely.

It can be concluded that students have three characteristics that differentiate them from each other: readiness, interest, and learning profile. It can be seen that students learn better if the tasks given in learning activities match the abilities they have in understanding a topic (readiness), the tasks given can trigger curiosity or passion in students (interest), and the tasks encourage participants. educate to work in the preferred way (learning profile). In this sub-chapter and the second sub-chapter that follows, the basics of differentiating instruction in responding to these three differences will be discussed.

One action that is believed to be a solution in addressing the heterogeneous conditions of students in one class is to apply a differentiated learning model. Where the learning model is directed at creating a system that can accommodate all students' uniqueness and needs. This system contains literacy and numeracy, stages of knowledge mastery, potential interests, and different learning styles through diagnostic assessments to gain a complete understanding of the uniqueness and needs of students. (Kristiani et al., 2021, p. 2)

Tomlinson (2001), Differentiated learning is an effort to adapt the learning process in the classroom to meet the individual learning needs of each student. Another expression for differentiated learning is the provision of a diverse class that provides opportunities to obtain content, process ideas and improve the learning outcomes of each student, so that they can learn effectively (Setiyo, 2022) in (Miqwati et al., 2023, p. 31)

Differentiated learning is in line with the philosophy of educational thought according to Ki Hajar Dewantara, that education (opvoeding) provides guidance for all the natural strengths that children have so that children are able to achieve the highest safety and happiness both as humans and as members of society. (Herwina, 2021 , p. 178).

The general aim of differentiated learning according to (Marlina, 2020) is to coordinate learning that emphasizes aspects of students' learning interests, students' readiness for learning and learning preferences. Specifically, differentiated learning includes 5 objectives, the first; 1) provide assistance to all students in achieving learning goals; 2) increasing student motivation through learning stimuli so that student learning outcomes increase; 3) establishing harmonious relationships in the learning process so that students are more enthusiastic; 4) stimulate students to become independent learners and have an attitude of respect for diversity; 5) to increase teacher satisfaction because there is a sense of challenge in learning so that they are more creative and want to develop their teaching competence. (Faiz et al., 2022, pp. 2849–2850).

Things that teachers must do to be able to implement differentiated learning in the classroom include: (Miqwati et al., 2023, p. 31)

1. Grouping students' learning needs based on three aspects which include willingness to learn, interest in learning and student learning profiles. This can be done by teachers by conducting interviews, observations or surveys, etc.
2. Teachers make different choices in terms of strategies, materials and learning methods that will appear in different learning designs based on survey results.
3. The teacher evaluates and reflects on the learning that has taken place with the students.

In differentiated learning there are three curricular elements, namely content differentiation, process differentiation and product differentiation. It is difficult and somewhat unnatural to separate curricular elements from content, process, and product, because students process ideas as they read content, think as they create products, and generate ideas for products as they encounter ideas in the material they study. use. However, figuring out how to differentiate teaching is easier to do by examining one element at a time. Just proceed with the awareness that these elements are more interconnected than they appear here.

In the differentiation of content and process, various strategies can be used, but what must be considered is adapting the content to the readiness, interests and learning profiles of students that are suitable for you and your students. The goal when differentiating content is to offer an approach to “input” (information, ideas, and skills) that meets individual students where they are and passionately supports their forward progress.

Then product differentiation by giving product assignments by paying attention to the different abilities of students is very useful. If all products relate to the same key information and understanding, then all students can share the information among individuals, small groups, or the whole class. This can happen even though working students have their own levels of readiness, interests, and ways of learning. By offering variations on well-designed products that share a common core, teachers encourage all students to capitalize on their personal interests and strengths. In this way, all students can grow from appropriate challenges. At the same time, teachers remain focused on curricular components that are considered important for all students.

A teacher's capacity to create a learning environment that is “invitational” for each student is a powerful contributor to student success. A teacher's capacity to enlist the partnership of students in creating and implementing classroom routines and processes that balance flexibility and predictability is essential. Such a balance is key if the class is to truly think about and understand content

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rather than merely repeat it; it also allows the class to make room for the individual learning differences apparent in most contemporary classrooms.

Arabic language learning, the success of which is greatly influenced by the basic abilities and characteristics of different students' interests, will be very appropriate if carried out using a differentiated learning model, where the teacher will act as needs diagnose as well as formulating appropriate and wise actions to be applied to each student. in order to achieve equal quality learning outcomes for all students.

All three forms of assessment—pre-assessments, formative assessments, and summative assessments—should be used in service of student learning. Some experts on assessment and measurement distinguish between assessment *of* learning, assessment *for* learning, and assessment *as* learning. Pre-assessments and formative assessments are often described as assessments *for* learning—that is, they help the teacher plan for better focused or more targeted instruction than would likely occur without the information about student learning the assessments reveal. Summative assessment is generally described as assessment *of* learning. It asks how well the student has achieved mastery of The clearly articulated learning goals—and then the class moves on.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses a quantitative approach with the Classroom Action Research method. Shiyami (2018) states that PTK can be a problem solving strategy by implementing real actions and exploring problem tracking and solving skills. In the educational context, PTK means combining meaningful action with research procedures to solve problems while using scientific references that will strengthen the solution. In this research, differentiated learning is implemented using a differentiated learning strategy, namely content, process and product differentiation. (Miqwati et al., 2023, p. 33).

One strategy that can be used in differentiated learning is the scaffolding strategy. Kim (2018) said that learning with scaffolding strategies is different from other teaching support strategies and tools in terms of what students intend to get out of difficulties, the timing of support, and the form of support. First, scaffolding needs to support current performance but also target students' ability to perform learning skills independently in the future. Second, scaffolding is used when students are involved with authentic/unstructured problems. Third, scaffolding needs to (a) build on what students already know and (b) be tied to ongoing assessment of students' abilities. The stages of the scaffolding strategy in learning are as follows: (Kusmaryono, 2021, pp. 30–31).

Implementation of the scaffolding strategy in learning is carried out following the steps in Figure 2: (1) asking questions; (2) presentation of problems for students to solve. (3) asking students to express what they know; (4) giving students the opportunity to re-examine their work; (5) ask students to describe a problem solving plan; (6) asking students to combine their ideas; (7) ask students to share (communicate with other students); (8) the teacher provides questions and key words; (9) If students need further information, the teacher guides students to return to step 4, and start again until the result is achieved. (Kusmaryono et al., 2020, p. 14)

This research was carried out at MTsN 1 Bengkalis. The instrument used in this research is the learning outcomes test. The data that has been collected from the learning outcomes test is then analyzed using descriptive statistical analysis. Learning outcome data is quantitative data realized by Arabic language learning results obtained through written tests which are carried out at the end of each meeting. Quantitative data analysis uses descriptive analysis. The criteria for passing learning outcomes can be seen in table 1

Table 1. Graduate Criteria

Skor	Kategori
$0 \leq x < 67$	tidak Tuntas
$67 \leq x \leq 100$	Tuntas

Winarni (2018)

For quantitative analysis, it is calculated using a simple statistical formula to determine student learning outcomes as follows:

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum x}{n}$$

Note: $\bar{X}$: Average
 $\sum x$: Number of values
n : Number of values

Arikunto (2012)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Differentiated learning is a teaching and learning process where students can learn subject matter according to their abilities, likes and needs so that they do not get frustrated and feel like they have failed in their learning experience (Tomlinson, 2017). There

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are five basic principles that help teachers implement differentiated learning, namely learning environment, quality curriculum, continuous assessment, responsive teaching and leadership and routines in the classroom (Kristiani et al., 2021, pp. 20–22).

A teacher's ability to create an “inviting” learning environment (Hattie, 2009) for each student is a strong contributor to student success. There is also no doubt that the teacher's ability to enlist student partnerships in creating and implementing classroom routines and processes that balance flexibility and predictability is critical. Such a balance is key if the class is to truly think about and understand the content rather than simply repeating it. (Tomlinson & Imbeau, 2015, pp. 2–3).

The steps used to create this learning environment are the first to use diagnostic tests to map students' interests and learning profiles. Students take cognitive and non-cognitive tests in the form of surveys through trigger questions. After getting the data, then design Differentiated Learning. In the first phase, namely the preparation phase, at this stage the teacher raises a problem and the students analyze it. The second phase is the presentation phase, at this stage the teacher assigns students to design (plan) the solution (individual learning) and the teacher helps students communicate ideas, in this phase the teacher also forms groups according to the students' learning profiles obtained from the initial diagnostic test. The third phase is the reflection phase, at this stage the teacher assigns students to exchange opinions with their colleagues and compare their opinions with each other (peerscaffolding) then the teacher uses scaffolding to provoke students' thinking to think more actively (one-to-one scaffolding), after that The teacher negotiates with all students. And at the end of the session students make their own conclusions (generalization of concepts).

The following are the comparative results of descriptive statistical analysis, namely the results of students' Arabic learning after being treated using differentiated learning through a scaffolding strategy. For descriptive statistical analysis, it can be seen in table 2.

Table 2. Comparison of Descriptive Statistical Analysis Results for Cycle I and Cycle II

Statistics	Posttest Statistical Values Cycle I	Posttest Statistical Values Cycle II
Maximum Score	75	86
Minimum Score	48	65
Ideal Score	100	100
KKM	67	67
Average Score	61	74

A comparison of students' Arabic learning outcomes categorized based on learning completeness can be seen in table 2. The impact of learning practices that have been implemented using the scaffolding strategy, namely an increase in student learning outcomes, when compared between cycle 1 and cycle 2.

Table 3. Comparison of descriptions of the completeness of Arabic language learning outcomes after being given treatment in Cycle I and Cycle II

Score	Category	Percentage Cycle I	Percentage Cycle II
$0 \leq x < 67$	Not Completed	66%	6%
$67 \leq x \leq 100$	Complete	34%	94%
Total		100%	100%

Based on table 3, it can be interpreted that the criteria for a student to be declared complete if the student has a score of at least 67. In cycle I, the percentage of students who could not meet the individual completeness criteria was 66% of the total number of students, while the percentage of students who could meet the individual completeness criteria by 34%. In Cycle II, the percentage of students who could not meet the individual completeness criteria was 6% of the total number of students, while the percentage of students who could meet the individual completeness criteria was 94%. If linked to the indicators of completeness of student learning outcomes, it can be concluded that the mathematics learning outcomes of class VII students at MTsN 1 Bengkalis after implementing differentiated learning through the Scaffolding Strategy have met the classical indicators of completeness of student learning outcomes, namely above 85%. According to (Trianto, 2009), a class is said to have completed learning (classical completeness) if in that class there are $\geq 85\%$ of students who have completed their learning. (Hirza et al., 2022, p. 27) So it can be concluded that there was an increase in Arabic language learning outcomes from cycle I to cycle II by 40% after being given treatment using differentiated learning through the Scaffolding Strategy.

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CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research that has been carried out, it can be concluded that the application of differentiated learning with the scaffolding strategy in learning Arabic at MTsN 1 Bengkalis can improve student learning outcomes. The increase in student Arabic learning outcomes can be seen from the average percentage of completeness of student learning outcomes in cycle I of 66%, which has increased to 94% in cycle II.

In its implementation, teachers must be confident in developing differentiated learning with scaffolding strategy. Because each different content requires different strategies or methods, coupled with various student learning styles. Differentiated learning can attract students' interest in learning and active participation.

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